

PROBLEMS OF USE OF TECHNICAL TERMINOLOGY IN TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION OF THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

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Annotation: *Over the past hundred years, humanity has created a huge leap in its evolutionary development. The term scientific and technological period is detected additional and more often in numerous areas of human life. This can be particularly noticeable within the leading branches of engineering and, in particular, the automotive-technological industry.*

Key words: *Exclusive mechanism, apprehensible, automotive industry, International standards, translation agency, inherent abbreviation, backdrop, semantic convergence, lexical units, descriptive construction, non-equivalent terms*

In a word, such a way becomes an exclusive mechanism in terms of engineering, the life cycle of that is in the course of varied terms, typically even troublesome to pronounce. During this regard, the connection of "decoding" terms into a language apprehensible to an oversized variety of motorists, and even a lot of therefore translation from a remote language into their native one, is of explicit importance.

Unfortunately, many professional linguists working with this topic state the fact that at present there is an insufficient number of specialized dictionaries on automotive terminology and, as a result, errors appear in translated technical documents and instructions that could have been avoided if appropriate glossaries were available. It is no exaggeration to note that such mistakes can have dire consequences. This leads to the conclusion that it is necessary to tighten control over the correct translation of terms in the automotive industry.

Here I would like to note that so as to translate complex technical documentation, saturated with special terms and meeting all international standards and requirements, one should turn to a native speaker with a technical education. Involving a high-class foreign translator in the translation of such

documents will be the key to successful work with the customer. Therefore, in order to translate complex technical documents, the Tech-Perewod.RU translation agency cooperates with highly professional linguists who are native speakers. There provided a full range of linguists involved in the research of technical translations identify a number of problems that may arise when translating highly specialized texts containing a large number of terms:

- Multiple and ambiguous interpretation of the term;
- The presence of two or more synonyms for the term itself;
- The presence in the translated text of a large number of abbreviations and abbreviations that may be inherent only in the original language;
- Making a decision by the translator on the choice of the way of translating the terms.

In their articles, philologists emphasize the matter of choosing a method for translating a term and attach special importance to this. In this regard, it makes sense to consider this issue in more detail.

Fig.1. Growth graph Efficiency of the automotive industry against the backdrop of the introduction of technical terminology in the automotive industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan

So, experts identify several ways of translating terms, such as:

- To search and find in the target language of the equivalent concept in the source language.

This method is recommended to be used if the countries of the source language and the target language are approximately at the same levels of socio-political and economic development.

- The appearance of a new term in the target language may occur under the influence of the corresponding concept of the source language. Linguists call this phenomenon - semantic convergence.

- The use of previously existing lexical units for the translation of terms and, as a result, the emergence of new words and phrases.

- The process of borrowing, when during translation a lexical unit with meaningful and formal features passes from the source language into the target language.

- A descriptive construction must be used to translate a term. This is usually used to translate non-equivalent terms.

Overall, I would like to emphasize that language is a living and non-stopped feature that is constantly developing and improving. Therefore, a specialist translating complex technical texts, especially in the automotive industry, must always "keep abreast" and keep track of all changes taking place in it.

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